

The Role of Time and Lorentz Invariances in the Quantum Wavelength

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In general, x and t are considered free variables taking on all real values (with $t > 0$). A particle's velocity may be calculated from $x(t)$. For the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ one may consider E for a free particle to follow from $\int F dx$ and p from $\int F dt$. If one wishes to put these on an equal footing, then $F dx$ requires a dt and $F dt$ a dx . This means t is replaced with dt and x with dx in $-Et + px$. What does it mean to have t and x intervals associated with a specific E, p and continuous $x(t)$ motion? There does not seem to be either an x or t interval. There are, however, dx and dt intervals associated with the creation of E and p from $p=0$. In other words, these dt, dx intervals are physically real properties just like p and E and are manifested experimentally.

If one imposes time reversal symmetry, not only should these intervals represent a kind of probability, but they should be symmetric. Thus, $x=0$ and $t=0$ are starting points such that $A=0$. A is a Lorentz invariant and so the end point should also have $A=0$ for time reversal to apply. This time reversal leads to two symmetric distributions, one in time with \hbar/E as a period and one in space with \hbar/p as a wavelength. This, however, does not show the direction of motion, say in the spatial distribution. Thus the symmetric x -probability distribution should ultimately be linked to both p and $-p$ i.e. should have a vector nature, although this has to be formally proved.

A full x -probability distribution linked with p should show the direction of motion. One may write $F(px)$ for the even symmetric function described above and $G(px)$ and $G(-px)$ for skewed full probability distributions such that $G(px) + G(-px) = 2F(px)$. This implies $G(px) = F(px) + B(px)$ where B is an odd function. We discussed the idea of $G(px)$ being the sum of an odd and even function in previous notes, but did not try to give a reason why $F(px)$ should be an even function with probability endpoints of 0. In this note, we argue that this is due to time reversal invariance.

A free Newtonian particle follows $x = vt$ and this should hold on average for a quantum particle which travels through space measured by an external ruler and clock. Above, however, we discussed probability distributions due to p . In fact their sharpness d/dx is proportional to p . How does one eliminate x dependence? As we argued in a previous note (2), one may take the AND condition $G(px)G(-px)$ which should remove all motion. This should be a constant. It is not just motion which is removed, but overall impulse which is the cause of the x -distributions. The square nature of $G(px)G(-px)$ explains why quantum mechanics deals with square root probabilities. These are the probabilities which are linked to impulse, hence to interactions, but the spatial distribution $\cos(px)$ from $\exp(ipx)$, does not describe the motion $x=vt$ which is also real. The problem, as we show, is that $G(px)$ cannot be real. This forces one to adopt a two dimensional probability and ultimately obtain $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the two dimensional vector one might expect.

Lorentz Invariance $A = -Et + px$

We have argued many times (starting with (1)), that the quantum period and wavelength follow from $A = -Et + px$, namely:

Period = \hbar/E and wavelength = \hbar / P

where \hbar is a constant linked to a photon which also follows $-Et+px$. ((1))

This result, however, seems ad hoc. X and t are supposed to be continuous variables with the relation $x(t)$ so why should one have a discrete time scale and a discrete length scale? In a previous note, we called these the internal clock and ruler gradation of a particle. Here we wish to consider an additional idea.

We begin with a hand-wavy observation namely that in the nonrelativistic case:

$Et \rightarrow (\text{Integral } Fdx)$ and there is an associated dt ((2a))

$Px \rightarrow (\text{integral } F dt)$ and there is an associated dx ((2b))

Thus in a handwavy sense t and x are linked to intervals dt and dx which in turn are linked to E and p . In other words, we suggest, as we have done before, that information of the interaction which created p, E from $m_0, p=0$ is retained in a moving particle. Not only that, but it is critical in describing reactions of the particle (say with a two slit etc).

How does one express dt and dx ? A moving particle has p, E , but doesn't have an x -interval or t -interval in Newtonian mechanics, but we argue that it carries these properties just like it carries E and p . $A = -Et+px$ may be thought of as x and t being continuous variables with $x/t = v$ OR one may think of $A = -E dt + p dx$ with E, p, dt and dx being properties of the moving object with $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$. Experiment seems to bear this out.

Given that a particle moves as $x=vt$ on average, what is happening with $dx=\hbar/p$ and $dt=\hbar/E$? Their ratio does not yield v (velocity). Rather these intervals carry information about the interaction which created the particle and may be imparted as an impulse at any instant (upon collision).

In previous notes we argued that dx must be defined by initial and end probabilities of 0 i.e must be in the form of a symmetric hump which may be extended into a $\sin(px)$ type of form. There should, however, be an argument for this symmetry.

Consider $A = -Et+px$ and $t=0, x=0$. Then $A=0$. There are however, $dx=\hbar/p$ and $dt=\hbar/E$ points (i.e. these and multiples) which also yield $A=0$. If one considers time reversal invariance, one would expect the probability at $x=0, t=0$ equal that at $x=\hbar/p$ and $t=\hbar/E$. One may then arbitrarily set this value to 0 and consider a repeated scheme through space. This, however, shows no direction of motion. Thus we argue that:

Time reversal symmetry suggests an x -probability distribution $F(px)$ which is symmetric and 0 at its endpoints. Repeating this in space yields a sine like pattern ((3))

The Case of Motion

The symmetric $F(px)$ whose derivative d/dx or sharpness in x space is proportional to the impulse hit p (like $-dV/dx$ is force) does not give any indication of the direction of motion, but an impulse i.e. does have a direction - it is a vector.

We argued that a moving particle has a dx region linked to the impulse that created it. This dx region is associated with a probability distribution. $F(px)$ is a real symmetric function which may take on positive and negative values (if it is of a sine type form). It, however, does not describe the vector nature of p . Thus it cannot be the complete picture. It is possible that $F(px)$ may be replaced with a vector in order to embody the vector nature of p , but first we assume a real function $G(px)$ which is skewed to describe full motion such that:

$$G(px) + G(-px) = 2F(px) \quad ((4))$$

We now consider $x=vt$ which treats all x points equally. How does the x -distribution $G(px)$ go away? It is there as a manifestation of an impulse, but an impulse is related to an interaction. There is no external interaction occurring as the particle moves along as $x=vt$. The solution, as we have argued in (2), is to take an AND probability combination:

$$G(px) G(-px) = \text{constant} \quad ((5))$$

This means one simultaneously imparts a p and $-p$ impulse i.e. no impulse and so has no information of an impulse and no x -probability distribution in space.

((4)), however, implies that: $G(px) = F(px) + B(px)$ where $B(px)$ is an odd function ((6))

((5)) becomes $(F+B)(F-B) = FF - BB$ i.e. a difference of squares ((7))

The problem with this is that for F even near $x=0$, F decreases while B increases. Thus $FF-BB$ becomes a smaller number as one moves from $x=0$ to the right, but this implies x dependence. Thus $G(px)$ cannot be a real number. We may then consider it to be a two dimensional vector (i.e. complex number) which is in keeping with the idea that p is a vector with two directions p and $-p$. The probability distribution embodies this two directional situation. Then:

$$G(px) = F(px) + i B(px) \text{ with } F(px) \text{ even, } B(px) \text{ odd} \quad ((8))$$

$$((5)) \text{ yields } BB + FF = \text{constant in } x \text{ or } BdB/dx = -F dF/dx \quad ((9))$$

A periodic solution is $B=\cos(px)$ and $F = \sin(px)$ or $G(px) = \exp(ipx)$.

Why Does Quantum Mechanics Use the Square Root of Probability i.e. $W^*(x)W(x)$ versus $W(x)$?

It is well-known that a quantum mechanical wavefunction, $W(x)$, is sometimes called a square root probability because $P(x) = \text{probability to be at } x = W^*(x)W(x)$. This is considered to be peculiar. In this note we argue that $W(x)=\exp(ipx)$ is associated with the impulse which created the momentum p in the first place. P is a vector with two directions p and $-p$ and $\exp(ipx)$ is also a vector associated with two directions. $\exp(ipx)$ describes the manner in which impulse interactions occur as demonstrated by a variety of experiments such as a 2 slit experiment etc and this involves x -distributio. We argued that the two x -probability distributions $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ associated with $\exp(ipx)$ are representative of the impulse. How does this answer the question of the square root of probability? In order to freeze out an impulse (i.e. apply p and $-p$ at the same place) so that there is no x distribution i.e. to make the picture consistent with $x=vt$, one has to multiply $\exp(-ipx)$ by $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. in a sense square the time reversed probabilities associated with impulse distributions to create $\text{Probability}(x)$ which does not show p (impulse) information.

The Notion of Equilibrium

In this section, we speculate the following. We argued above for a symmetric probability distribution $F(px)$ using time reversal invariance which is associated with both forward and backward motion. We now note that in a usual Newtonian equilibrium there is a function:

$$Q(x) \text{ such that } Q(x+dx) = Q(x) + 0 + dx \frac{dQ}{dx} + \dots \quad ((10))$$

Thus the first derivative vanishes and one has an equilibrium situation. $F(px)$ is a function which is repeated in space like a sine wave and its derivative d/dx is not zero in general. One, however, may consider:

$$F(px) \text{ and } F(px+pdx) \quad ((11))$$

If $F(px)$ represents an equilibrium scenario, one may suggest that the Newtonian ((10)) be replaced with:

$$\text{Integral } F \frac{dF}{dx} = 0 \quad ((12)) \text{ i.e. } F(px+pdx) = F(x) + pdx \frac{dF}{dx}$$

and this change does not lead to any overlap or change to first order. Thus $F(px)$ is in a kind of equilibrium state. This approach then becomes associated with conservation of momentum because each $F(p1x)$, $F(p2x)$ etc is in its own unique equilibrium state and there is no overlap:

$$\text{Integral } F(p1x) F(p2x) dx = 0 \quad ((13))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, although a number of ideas here have been considered in the past, we wish to focus on Lorentz and time reversal invariance. Lorentz invariance of $A = -Et + px$ may immediately lead in an ad hoc way to $t = \hbar/E$ and $x = \hbar/p$ as intervals associated with E and p which keep $A = 0$. What do they really mean, however? X and t are supposed to be continuous variables such that $x = vt$. We argue that a moving particle not only has E and p as properties, but also $dx = \hbar/p$ and $dt = \hbar/E$ and experiment bears this out. What does it mean to say that a particle has an interval dx ? We suggest that this implies an x -probability distribution linked to the impulse p . By using time reversal symmetry we suggest a symmetric function $F(px)$, but this does not describe the direction of motion. Momentum p is a vector with two directions and we argue that likewise $F(px)$ should be replaced with a two vector linked to two directions of motion i.e. $G(px)$ and $G(-px)$ such that $G(px) + G(-px) = 2F(px)$. It has to be proved, however, that the distribution is a vector. If one at first considers $G(px)$ to be real and skewed in the positive direction and $G(-px)$ skewed in the negative and tries to remove motion i.e. impulse through $G(px)G(-px)$ one sees that $G(px)$ cannot be real. Instead one should have a two dimensional vector (linked to the two directions of p , p and $-p$) i.e. $G(px) = F(px) + iB(px)$ where $B(px)$ is odd. Then: $FF + BB = \text{constant}$ and $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ is a solution.

References

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